

ISic0003

Epitaph for Culucuitas

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in area of Piazza Stesicoro (area of a Roman necropolis)

Coordinates

37.507453, 15.085762

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3503

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · Man (ibus) · Culuc uitas · vix (it) · an (nis) · II ·
3. Tyche · et · Herma · fe (cerunt)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Culucuitas lived for 2 years. Tyche and Herma made this.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491590

EDR 141191

EDCS 21900419

Bibliography

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